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Workshop: Propagating DEM Uncertainty to Stream Extraction using GRASS

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Abstract — GRASS is an open-source geospatial processing engine. With over 400 tools available in the core distribution and an additional 400+ tools available as extensions, GRASS has broad applicability in the Earth Sciences and geomorphometry in particular. In this workshop, we will give an introduction to GRASS and demonstrate some of the geomorphometry tools available in GRASS. Specifically, we will show how to compute stream extraction uncertainty using a workflow adapted from Hengl (2007) [1] and Hengl (2010) [2]. We will begin by downloading publicly available LiDAR data of the Perugia area using GRASS data fetching tools. Then, we will use R's kriging functions (`gstat`) to create 100 iterations of a DEM. After exploring some of the stream extraction and flow routing methods available in GRASS, we will extract streams from each of the 100 DEMs to compute stream uncertainty. The workshop will be conducted in a Jupyter Notebook hosted in Google Colab. By the end of the workshop, participants will have hands on experience with:

- Creating GRASS projects and importing datasets
- Adjusting the computational extent and resolution
- Creating DEMs from point data using a variety of methods implemented in GRASS and using a stochastic kriging approach in R
- Using the R interface for GRASS and R packages with GRASS data
- Computing Stream Uncertainty
- Developing publication-quality figures with `grass.jupyter`

I. GRASS BACKGROUND

GRASS is an open source geoprocessing engine and GIS software that is widely used by researchers in academia, industry and government. Its over 800 tools provide geospatial algorithms for a wide range of applications including hydrology, remote sensing, image classification and segmentation, data visualization, point cloud processing and spatio-temporal analysis [3]. For geomorphometry, GRASS provides many relevant sets of tools including DEM generation and interpolation tools, various spatial statistics including curvature,

aspect and geomorphon classification, many different flow direction and accumulation tools and extensive hydrology tools.

GRASS offers many different interfaces for accessing its library of tools. The basic installation of GRASS includes a Graphical User Interface, command line interface, C API and Python API. There is also a R API (`rgrass`) [4] that can be installed through CRAN and a plugin for QGIS. In this workshop, we will introduce participants to the command line interface, Python API and R API.

Finally, because of GRASS's modular architecture, it is easy to create custom tools within the GRASS environment, making it a powerful tool for open science. Using GRASS's standardized tool interface, users can create their own standalone tools or contribute their novel algorithms and tools to the GRASS addons repository. Tools contributed to the GRASS addons repository are maintained by the community ensuring continued functionality. During the workshop, we will use tools written by researchers, learn how to cite them and where to find more information.

II. WORKSHOP CONTENTS

The workshop material will be provided as a downloadable Jupyter Notebook and online through Google Colab [5]. All data will be provided through online resources. Participants can choose to work on their local machine (Windows, MacOS, or Linux) or through Google Colab. For running the notebooks locally, we recommend at least 5 GB of storage space, 16GB of RAM, and a modern processor.

The workflow will use a combination of GRASS tools and R tools. In particular, we demonstrate both the R (`rgrass`) and Python (`grass.script`) GRASS APIs and how to move between the languages in one notebook and in one GRASS session.

A. Getting Started with GRASS

We will create a new GRASS project for the Perugia, Italy region using the GRASS Python API. The project's coordinate reference system (CRS) will be set to WGS 84/UTM zone 32N (EPSG:32632). We will import data from the TINITALY DEM (TINITALY 1.1) dataset [6] and set GRASS's computational region to a spatial resolution of 10-meters and spatial extent defined by coordinates: north=4780470; south=4774720; east=783130; west=777410 (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Subset of TINITALY DEM (10 m) tile (w47575).

Here, we will learn how to resample, evaluate, and visualize our DEM data using both the `grass.scripts` and `grass.jupyter` Python libraries.

B. DEM Uncertainty and DEM Generation with Stochasticity

Stream uncertainty arises from differences between a DEM and the actual surface [7]. DEMs created from sparse points force us to interpolate the surface in between the points. Additionally, datasets created from LiDAR data can have areas of low point density (i.e. waterbodies or dense vegetation), creating another case where we may need to interpolate a surface. This interpolation introduces uncertainty into the flow path of the stream.

To simulate this phenomenon in the workshop, we will sample points from the TINItaly DEM dataset [6] and use an isotropic model variogram to measure the spatial dependence of elevation points. The TINItaly DEM provides a 10m DTM with an overall root mean square error (RMSE) less than 3.5 m [6]. To create a

point dataset, we randomly sample points from the DEM using the GRASS Python API. Then, we move this point layer into R where we will access the current GRASS session using `rgrass` [4]. Along with `rgrass::read_VECT` and `sf`, we use the `gstat` library to plot an empirical variogram and fit an isotropic model variogram using the Matern covariance function (Fig. 2a).

Leveraging the fitted model and observed elevation points, we perform a stochastic spatial simulation using the conditional Gaussian simulation (CGS) method [1, 2]. A total of 100 surface realizations will be generated using the `gstat::predict` tool, allowing the assessment of error propagation from the spatial uncertainty of the interpolated surfaces [1].

C. Propagation of Uncertainty to Stream Extraction in GRASS

Finally, we write the simulated DEMs back into the GRASS project using `rgrass::write_RAST` and compute the resulting flow accumulation paths and stream networks. We calculate the stream network of each simulated DEM using GRASS's `r.watershed` tool [8] with the `rgrass::execGRASS` R function. We will then calculate the uncertainty of the 100 different stream networks by first calculating the probability of a stream using GRASS's `r.series` and `r.mapcalc` tools [3]. Finally, we quantify per-pixel classification uncertainty across the stochastic simulations using the binary entropy function:

$$H_i = -P_i \log(P_i) - (1 - P_i) \log(1 - P_i)$$

where P_i is the empirical probability of classification for cell i . This calculation, based on Shannon entropy [9], captures the inherent uncertainty associated with binary classification outcomes [1, 2] as shown in Fig. 2(c).

C. Publication Ready figures with GRASS Jupyter

Throughout the workshop, we will visualize data using the `grass.jupyter` package [10], a recently-developed package that contains many different visualization tools and can be combined with other Python libraries such as `Matplotlib` to create publication quality figures. We will also demonstrate some of the interactive visualization widgets which can be exported as HTML files and shared on websites or standalone digital data visualizations.

(a)

(c)

Figure 2. An empirical variogram (a), standard deviation of kriged DEMs (b) and stream uncertainty (c) made with the workshop TINITALY DEM.

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(b)

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